

Characterization and Optimization of a Novel Electromagnetic Transduction Technique for Rotational Energy Harvesting

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Abstract – A novel transduction technique that converts mechanical rotation energy to usable electrical energy using condensed magnetic flux is tested and characterized for a wind source. This rotation harvester is compared to the power output of a commercially available generator for a fixed wind source. Optimization of the rotation harvester is discussed in terms of various parameters, such as magnet spacing, number of excitation arms, rotation frequency, and harvester resonance.

enclosed by the coil. For the SSC Pacific energy harvester configuration, the magnetic gradient is increased by condensing the flux between two like-poled magnets as in Fig.1. The magnets are rigidly attached and free to move, via springs, relative to the coil between them. Previous efforts at SSC Pacific have optimized and measured higher power outputs than single magnet / single coil configurations [3], [4], [5].

I. INTRODUCTION

Many applications for energy harvesting involve sources that are rotational, such as wind, fluid flow, and rotating machinery. It is desirable to convert the available rotation kinetic energy into electric energy delivered to a load as efficiently as possible. Total system efficiency for wind power is often 20% or less [1]. Up to this time, standard electro-inductive generation techniques have been applied to harness this energy, using individual magnet/coil flux capture. Space and Naval Warfare Systems Center Pacific (SSC Pacific) has developed a novel electromagnetic configuration (U.S. Patent #7,501,726) that results in a high flux gradient passing through a coil in response to mechanical motion [2]. This configuration has been applied to a rotational harvesting design, by creating a ring of harvesters that are excited by magnets affixed to an axial shaft. This rotational harvester has the potential to extract energy more efficiently than commonly used techniques, due to the increased magnetic flux density across the coil.

II. TRANSDUCTION METHOD

Electricity is generated by changing flux density passing through a coil, via Faraday’s Law,

$$V = N 2\pi f B(x,t) A. \quad (1)$$

Where V is the Voltage out, f is the frequency of vibration, B is the spatial magnetic field gradient, and A is the area

Figure 1. (Top) EH design with magnetic flux lines. (Bottom) EH dimensions; O.D. = Coil Outer Diameter, I.D. = Coil Inner Diameter, T = Coil Thickness, H = Magnet thickness, G = Magnet separation, D = Magnet Diameter.

Applying this harvesting method to capture rotational energy, a number of individual single axis harvesters are arranged along the circumference of a circle, as in Fig.2. These harvesters are fixed, and in the center is a free-spinning “exciter”, to which is attached a multiple of magnetic arms.

Figure 2. Rotational Harvester configuration, with eight diametric harvesters and five exciter arms on the central axis. Exciter arm magnets and harvester magnets have opposing fields.

The magnets on the arms are oriented in such a way as to repel the magnets of the individual harvesters as they rotate. Each individual harvester has a resonant frequency based on the mass of its magnets and spring constant. For rotation testing with multiple harvesters, the springs are designed to be as similar as possible, within manufacturing error, such that the resonances match to within a few Hertz.

III. EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

For the experimental setup, a platform was constructed with slots for up to 8 harvesters, and up to 5 rotating magnetic exciter arms (Fig.3). The spacing between the harvesters and the exciter arms can be adjusted. The exciter can be driven via a belt and motor or wind turbine. An optical sensor tracks the arm rotation frequency.

Figure 3. Experimental rotation setup, with belt driven rotation axis.

For testing with a wind source, a fan was placed 9" from a turbine which drives the exciter via the motor belt (Fig.4). The turbine was purchased from Four Seasons Windpower, LLC. An electrical generator was included with the turbine, which was also tested for comparison to the rotation harvester, by driving it with the same belt, turbine, and wind source (Fig.5).

Figure 4. Experimental setup for testing rotation harvester with wind source and turbine.

Figure 5. Experimental setup for testing commercial generator with wind source and turbine.

For rectification of the harvester AC output, Germanium diodes (0.2-0.3 forward Voltage) were implemented in full wave rectifiers for the rotation harvester, and in a 3-phase rectifier for the Four Seasons generator. In all measurements, power was measured across an ideal load.

IV. OPTIMUM TORQUE

Depending on the number of arms and arrangement of harvesters, there will be varying amounts of torque due to the opposing magnetic fields of the arms and harvesters. It is

desired to minimize the maximum torque in order to overcome starting inertia and reduce rotation resistance. If the arm configuration is symmetric with the harvesters, it is expected that there will be more maximum torque due to deeper potential wells, as seen by the magnetic arms. An even/odd arrangement of arms to harvesters would decrease maximum torque by spreading out the potential wells. In order to simulate this, Mathematica was used to model maximum torque and magnetic field due to different configurations of arms and harvesters. For simplification, the magnets are assumed to be fixed, and torque is calculated for a fixed spacing of inner to outer magnets (Fig.6a).

Figure 6a. Electromagnetic simulation to calculate axis torque and rotational resistance.

Figure 6b. Calculation of torque as a function of the number of inner and outer magnets. Lighter areas indicate higher torque. In this diagram the ration of outer to inner rings is 1.725.

As can be seen in Fig.6b, one configuration of low maximum torque is 8 harvesters and 5 magnet arms. This configuration was tested and compared with 4 magnet arms, which has relatively higher maximum torque.

V. MEASUREMENT AND ANALYSIS

A. Single Harvesters Driven by Motor

Two different harvester responses were tested in the rotation setup driven by a motor. The first (Type A), has a coil with 8,625 turns and resonance of about 18Hz. The second (Type B), has a coil with 21,150 turns and resonance of about 35Hz. Both have the same magnet to coil spacing.

For higher excitation forces, the magnets will begin to hit the coil as they vibrate. The closer the spacing between exciter arms and harvester magnets, the higher the input force to the harvester. Since Type B has a stiffer spring, the harvester can be placed closer to the magnet arms before rotation causes the harvester magnet to hit the coil. Closer spacing results in an exponentially increasing excitation force. The closest spacing tested for Type B (at 3.2mm) produced a maximum power delivered to the load of 43.7mW (see Fig.7).

Figure 7. Maximum power delivered to load, with rotational excitation from motor (harvester Type B).

Harvester output was also measured as a function of frequency. In this case, the frequency referred to is the rate at which magnet arms pass individual harvester magnets. The actual rotation rate of the axis can be found by dividing the frequency by the number of arms. The output is hysteretic, because of nonlinearity in the harvester springs due to stress during manufacture and assembly.

Shown in Fig.8 is the response due to varying the frequency from low to high with a motor. It can be seen that there are two peaks in the frequency response. The lower peak

corresponds to a sub-harmonic of the harvester resonance (at its corresponding effective acceleration). When the magnet arm passes at a sub-harmonic, it acts as an impulse that causes the harvester to resonate a whole number of cycles. The first sub-harmonic causes two cycles of vibration before the arm passes again, resulting in resonance at this frequency. The amplitude of the response at the sub-harmonic depends on the mechanical damping of the harvester. Plotted are the responses at two different separations of arms from the harvester. This is approximately the separation where the magnet begins to hit the coil at resonance. Smaller separation (and higher power) is possible, but the response given a particular input would be reduced in efficiency.

Figure 8. Harvester Type A frequency response to rotational excitation.

Figure 9. Harvester Type A frequency response to linear constant accelerations induced by shaker table.

Optimally, the harvester resonance and arm to harvester spacing should be chosen such that with an expected wind strength (or other source), the system is not often driven beyond resonance where the response is low.

Fig.9 shows the response of harvester Type A to induced acceleration via a shaker table. This allows rotation excitation to be correlated to an effective induced acceleration. In this configuration, the force induced by the rotating arms is equivalent to about 150 mg of acceleration, with a power output of 2 mW.

B. Multiple Harvesters Driven by Motor

For excitation of more than one harvester, there are various methods of combining the output powers of individual harvesters. A multi-phase rectifier is difficult to implement because there is no center tap to the coils. Nevertheless, harvesters can be connected with one lead in common, but only if the harvester outputs are in phase. This can only occur if the number of excitation arms equals the number of harvesters. Individual Germanium diode full wave rectifiers were used for each harvester, to ensure full rectification.

The DC outputs of each of the rectifiers can be connected in series or in parallel. If added in series, Voltage increases per harvester and the optimum load resistance increases in proportion to the number of outputs. If connected in parallel, the optimum resistance decreases and the overall Voltage is the same as a single harvester. Since the SSC Pacific harvesters produce plenty of Voltage individually (12 to 14 Volts for the configuration of Fig.8), the outputs were added in parallel. This has the added benefit of reducing the optimum load resistance, which is ideal for situations such as the charging of a capacitor for energy storage. As can be seen in Fig.10, the output powers roughly add with harvesters in parallel, although the combined resonance occurs at a lower frequency.

Figure 10. Frequency Response with individual harvesters and with harvester outputs connected in parallel.

C. Rotation Harvesting with Wind Source

With eight harvesters (Type A) connected in parallel, the power delivered to an optimum load was measured for different separations between rotating arms and harvesters. In addition, two different configurations of the number of rotating arms (4 and 5) were compared.

Figure 11. Power output with wind excitation, compared with commercial generator, for 2 exciter arm configurations.

As can be seen from Fig.11, the resulting power out is very different for the two different arm configurations. Overall, the power is higher with 5 arms, due to less torque. With 4 rotating magnet arms, the maximum torque is expected to be higher due to the presence of deeper magnetic potential wells occurring when the arms exactly line up between harvesters. Under the influence of the wind source, the arms would not rotate freely for the closest arm to harvester separation (at 3.2mm). For the next two closest separations, the arms had to be “kick-started” to overcome the potential well before rotating freely on their own. For the 5 arm configuration, the arms freely started and rotated on their own for all arm to harvester separations.

An interesting and unexpected phenomenon occurred during wind testing at various arm to harvester separations. For a wide range of separations, the harvesters would “lock on” to resonance. That is, negative feedback is somehow applied by the influence of the harvester vibrations themselves on the magnet arms that regulates the turbine speed, such that it rotates the arms at the harvester resonance. One would expect different rotation rates for different separations because of the reduction in torque seen by the system for larger spacing. However, for a range of separations, the turbine speed gradually increases until stabilizing at resonance. This occurred between about 15 and 22 mm with the 5 arm configuration and between 15 and 29 mm with 4 arms. This is good news for practical applications, because with the right

rotation harvester design, the rotation rate of the turbine will lock on to the system harvester resonance, where power is highest, regardless of the particular resonant frequencies of individual harvesters. This would allow quite a bit of flexibility in spring design, while taking advantage of increased power output due to resonance.

D. Commercial Generator with Wind Source

As a comparison, the power output of a Four Seasons generator that came with the wind turbine (Four Seasons Mini Vertical Axis Wind Turbine) was measured with the same wind source used for the rotation harvester wind testing. In both cases, the fan was placed at a distance of 9” from the turbine. The same motor belt that was connected from the turbine to the harvester rotating arms was used to turn the generator under the influence of wind, in order to eliminate belt friction as a variable. The output of the generator was rectified using the same Germanium diodes used for the rotation harvester.

In order to find the maximum power out, for the fixed wind source, the optimum load resistance for the generator was determined by varying the load resistor at the output of the rectifier until maximum power was observed, allowing the system to stabilize for each measurement point (Fig.12).

Figure 12. Optimum load power for commercial generator with fixed wind source.

The highest generator power out, with a 680Ω load, was 6.8mW, compared to 22.4mW from the rotation harvester, corresponding to a factor of 3.3 in performance improvement.

VI. OPTIMIZATION CONSIDERATIONS

It is desirable to have a harvester to arm separation such that the expected source will drive the harvester into frequencies at resonance or below, and not separated too much such that the system is driven out of resonance most of the time. This spacing can be tailored, and depends on the spring

constant of the harvesters and the number of rotating magnet arms. Stiffer springs will allow for closer spacing, and increasing the number of arms will drive harvesters with higher resonant frequencies, for a particular axial rotation. In addition, for optimum efficiency, the magnet separation within component harvesters should be designed such that the magnets do not hit the coil under typical source conditions.

The configuration of rotating arms should be such that maximum torque is minimized, primarily by using an even/odd number of harvesters to arms, in conjunction with proper simulation of magnetic potentials.

Damping of the harvesters should be minimized, so as to maximize the response to impulses at sub-harmonics of the harvester resonance, in order to capture the most energy for sources with variable input speeds.

The number of coil turns and wire gauge can be varied to customize the optimum load resistance and output Voltage for a fixed or average load. For scenarios involving charging a storage component, the harvester outputs should be connected in parallel in order to minimize the optimum load resistance.

VII. CONCLUSION

A functional rotation harvester has been constructed and tested, using SSC Pacific's novel transduction technique, and compared to an example commercial generator in terms of power delivered to an optimum load.

The effect of the number of magnetic exciter arms was simulated and experimentally explored for configurations of 4 and 5 arms. The 5 arm rotor performed the best, with self-starting, sustained rotation, and minimal torque.

Self-tuning of the system to harvester resonance with a wind driven turbine was observed for a range of arm to harvester separations.

Addition of the power outputs in parallel of individual harvesters was measured and magnetic excitation force was correlated with effective harvester linear acceleration. A maximum power out of 43.7mW was obtained with close spacing and driving motor.

The rotation harvester performance was demonstrated using a non-idealized design. Performance could be improved in future designs by proper selection of coil geometry, individual harvester magnet spacing, reduction of wasted space, and further improvement in exciter arm configuration.

Despite a non-idealized design, the rotation harvester outperformed the commercial harvester by a factor of 3.3, for identical wind source conditions.

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